

Morpho-physiological and Yield Characterization of Diverse Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) Varieties for Germplasm Enhancement

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Abstract:

The study aimed to characterize 104 genetically diverse rice landraces from different regions of India, evaluating their morpho-physiological, yield, grain quality, and phenology traits. Several of these landraces possess valuable traits for grain and nutritional quality and abiotic stress tolerances. Hence this research was conducted during the kharif season in 2022, focused on characterization, to help the breeders identify potential donors for enhancing rice yield with abiotic stress tolerance, and grain nutritional quality. The experiment utilized a randomized block design with three replications, observing 11 traits across five representative plants in each replication. Statistical analysis revealed significant variability among the landraces, emphasizing their diversity and potential for genetic improvement. Results highlighted moderate consistency in flowering time, with high variations for traits such as tillers and panicle numbers, grain length, breadth, and weight. Landraces like Swarnamasuri and Kalakuruvai exhibited high yield potential, making them valuable genetic resources for productivity enhancement. The study emphasized the importance of traits like panicle and grain numbers in influencing yield, with identified prolific landraces serving as ideal donors for improving these characteristics. The identified high-yielding landraces can contribute directly to cultivation, while genetically diverse accessions offer new sources of beneficial genes for broadening diversity in elite varieties. Overall, this study contributes valuable insights for breeders and researchers working towards enhancing rice productivity and quality.

Keywords: Rice, Germplasm, Genetic diversity, Landraces, Varietal characterization

I. Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is the most important cereal crop feeding more than half of the world's population. With the growing demand for rice from a growing population, there is a need to sustainably increase productivity and enhance genetic yield potential in rice (Mohanty, 2013). Utilization of genetic diversity is key to developing improved high yielding varieties that can perform well across diverse environments and stresses (Narayanan *et al.*, 2020).

India is home to a vast reserve of genetically diverse rice landraces which can serve as important donors for broadening the genetic base of elite breeding lines (Singh *et al.*, 2000). Rice landraces have evolved under low input farming over centuries and harbor many useful adaptive and nutritive genes. Characterization of landraces to identify sources of beneficial traits is thus important for their enhanced utilization in variety development programs (Upadhyaya *et al.*, 2009).

In this study, we characterized 104 genetically diverse rice landraces from various geographic regions of India for morpho-physiological, yield, grain quality and phenology related traits. The objective was to characterize the landraces, which in turn help breeders to identify promising landraces as donors for enhancing yield, abiotic stress tolerance and grain nutritional quality traits in rice. The promising donors identified can then be utilized readily in rice improvement programs while those exhibiting high diversity can be explored further to broaden the genetic base of elite breeding material.

II. Materials and Methods

A. Experimental Site and Season

The experiment was conducted at the V.O.C. Agricultural College and Research Institute, Killikulam, geographically located in 8°46' N latitude and 77°42' E longitude and at an altitude of 40 m above mean sea level (MSL) during Kharif, 2022.

B. Plant Material and experimental design

The plant material comprised of 104 genetically diverse rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) landraces obtained from various geographic locations in India (Table 1).

The 104 rice landraces were evaluated in a randomized block design with three replications. Seedlings were transplanted at one seedling per hill with a spacing of 20 cm × 15 cm under irrigated lowland conditions. Recommended agronomic package of practices were followed to raise a healthy crop. Necessary prophylactic measures were taken to control insect pests and diseases.

C. Observations Recorded

Observations were recorded on the following 11 morpho-physiological, yield, grain quality and phenology related traits in five representative plants from each replication at different crop growth stages.

1. Days to 50% flowering (DFP, days)
2. Plant height (PH, cm)
3. Number of tillers per plant (NT)
4. Number of panicles per plant (NPT)
5. Panicle length (PL, cm)
6. Number of filled grains per panicle (NFG)

7. Thousand grain weight (1000 GW, g)
8. Grain length (GL, mm)
9. Grain breadth (GB, mm)
10. Grain Length/breadth ratio (L/B ratio)
11. Single plant yield (SPY, g)

The data were analyzed statistically following standard procedures. Analysis of variance was performed on plot means basis to test for differences among the 104 landraces.

III. Results

Analysis of variance for all the eleven biometrical traits were shown significant differences and this showed that the genotypes are diverse in nature (Table 2). The genotypes evaluated in this study exhibit considerable variability in various agronomic traits, providing valuable insights into the diversity present in the landrace and variety populations. The mean values across all genotypes indicate an overall performance level for each trait (Table 3).

Days to 50% Flowering (DFF), the genotypes show an average of 87.13 days, 72.00 for Navara and 112.78 for Navara black was recorded as minimum and maximum mean values for days to 50% flowering, respectively, with a relatively low coefficient of variation (C.V.) of 5.13%. This suggests a moderate level of consistency in the flowering time among the evaluated genotypes. The standard error (S.E.) is 2.58 days, indicating the precision of the mean.

Number of Tillers (NT) and Number of Productive Tillers (NPT) are crucial traits related to the plant's ability to absorb and distribute nutrients. With average values of 23.67, maximum value of 71.01 was recorded for the genotype Virendra and 19.26, maximum of 52.54 for Navara, respectively, these traits exhibit moderate levels of variation (C.V. of 5.54% and 5.43%). The S.E. values of 0.76 and 0.60 indicate a reliable estimate of the mean.

Panicle Length (PL) and Number of Filled Grains per panicle (NFG) are key yield-contributing factors. The average PL is 21.96 cm, 29.22 and 10.91 was the highest and the lowest mean value recorded for Kaivara samba and Karuthanavara, respectively, with a C.V. of 5.14%, indicating moderate variation. NFG has an average of 127.77, highest mean value for the trait was recorded as 268.50 for purpleputtu and the C.V. is 5.42%, suggesting consistent performance among the genotypes for grain filling. The S.E. values (PL = 3.99 cm, NFG = 0.72) highlight the precision of the means.

The Thousand Grain Weight (1000GW) is an essential trait influencing overall grain yield. The genotypes exhibit an average of 21.57 grams, the highest and lowest mean value of 41.00 and 9.71 was recorded for Ariyan and Harathi, respectively, with a C.V. of 5.82%. The S.E. of 0.72 emphasizes the precision of this mean value.

Grain Length (GL), Grain Breadth (GB), and Grain Length-to-Breadth Ratio (L/B ratio) contribute to grain quality. The average GL is 7.29 mm, GB is 2.82 mm, and L/B ratio is 2.64. These traits show moderate variability with C.V. values ranging from 5.36% to 5.55%, and S.E. values ranging from 0.23, 0.09 and 0.08, indicating reliable estimates of the means.

Finally, Single Plant Yield (SPY) is an important yield component. With an average value of 49.15, this trait shows moderate variability (C.V. = 6.03%), the mean values were ranged between 11.48 and 116.42. The maximum mean value was registered for TPS 5 and the minimum was for Thanga samba and the S.E. of 1.71 emphasizes the precision of the mean (Table 3). The characterization of these genotypes reveals a diverse range of performance across multiple traits,

providing valuable information for breeders and researchers working towards enhancing rice productivity and quality. The moderate levels of variability suggest potential opportunities for targeted improvement in specific traits.

The significant variability observed among rice landraces for yield, yield traits, grain quality features and phenology highlights the wealth of diversity in indigenous germplasm which can aid in broadening and enhancing the genetic potential of rice cultivars.

IV. Discussion

The significant genetic variability observed among the rice landraces for grain yield and component characters in this study agrees well with earlier reports in rice germplasm collections (Upadhyaya *et al.*, 2014; Balakrishnan *et al.*, 2016). This highlights the diversity present in indigenous landraces as a reservoir of useful genes and variants for rice improvement. Grain yield is a complex entity influenced by several component traits with low to moderate heritability. The high yielding landraces identified in this study such as Swarnamasuri, Kalakuruvai, Orisa Kuttai Sivappu Arisi, Palkuda Vazhai and others represent an important genetic resource for enhancing productivity. Several studies have reported wide variation in grain yield among diverse rice accessions (Vanaja and Babu, 2006; Suryanarayana *et al.*, 2010).

Sink size representing the capacity to support grain filling is an important contributor to productivity differences in cereals. Traits like number of panicles per plant and number of grains per panicle which showed positive association with grain yield in the present study have been widely reported to influence sink strength and harvest index (Prasad *et al.*, 2001; Sandhu *et al.*, 2012). Selection for enhanced panicle number and grain number will thus raise yield potential. The prolific landraces Navara, Navara 957 and Noothipathu identified in this study are thus ideal donors for enhancing productive tiller number in elite breeding lines. Similarly high grain number landraces including Komban Samba, Ariyan 6333 and Swarnamasuri provide apt sources to improve grain number.

Several quantitative trait loci (QTLs) influencing yield and yield traits have been mapped in rice (Xing and Zhang, 2010). Marker assisted introgression of genomic regions harboring QTLs for grain and panicle traits from the promising landraces can aid precision breeding. High test weight landraces are also valuable donors for enhancing grain filling and meeting market specific demands for long slender or short bold grain types. Early maturing landraces enable rapid varietal turnover over seasons and hence higher productivity in restrictive environments. The high yielding landraces identified can be used directly in cultivation upon release as varieties after multilocation testing. The genetically diverse accessions characterized also provide new sources of beneficial genes and alleles for broadening diversity in popular elite varieties through crossing and selection.

V. Conclusion

In conclusion, the comprehensive characterization of 104 genetically diverse rice landraces from various regions of India revealed substantial variability in morpho-physiological, yield, grain quality, and phenology traits. This study emphasizes the importance of leveraging the rich genetic diversity inherent in indigenous landraces for enhancing rice productivity and quality. Promising high-yielding landraces such as Jaya, Kalakuruvai, Rajalakshmi, Navara, Noothipathu, Kullakar, Swarnamasuri, TPS 5, RpBioPatho2, TRY 3, ADT 37 Aryan 1203 and the other high yielding genotypes were identified as valuable genetic resources, offering potential contributions to productivity improvement. Traits like panicle and grain numbers were identified as crucial factors influencing yield, providing avenues for targeted enhancement.

Moreover, the observed genetic variability aligns with previous reports, underscoring the significance of indigenous landraces as reservoirs of useful genes for rice improvement. The identified landraces not only serve as direct contributors to cultivation but also offer opportunities for marker-assisted introgression to enhance specific traits. The study's findings support the broader goal of broadening the genetic base of elite breeding material, facilitating precision breeding for improved grain yield, quality, and stress tolerance. Overall, this research provides valuable insights for breeders and researchers working towards sustainable rice production and crop improvement strategies in the face of evolving environmental challenges.

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Table. 1 List of 104 Rice Genotypes under Study

S.No	Genotypes	S.No	Genotypes	S.No	Genotypes
01	Purpleputtu	46	Orisamani Samba	91	Harathi
02	Abiya	47	Sengalpattu Sirumani	92	Karthanavara
03	Chennakayamma	48	Aathurkicheli Samba	93	Chiruchitteni - 882
04	Shabhagidhan	49	Karuppu kavuni	94	Chomala – 2206
05	Vattan	50	Oriza Kuttai Sivappu Arisi	95	Aryan - 1204
06	Jaya	51	Ariyan	96	NL 24
07	Thamarai	52	Oheruchitteni	97	ASD 16
08	Sivappumalli	53	Chennellu 6806	98	RpBioPatho 1
09	Pisni	54	J – 13 100 days	99	TPS 5
10	Kalanamak	55	Mappillai Samba	100	RpBioPatho 2
11	Kalakuruvai	56	Kunju Kunju	101	TRY 3
12	Rajalakshmi	57	Navara Black	102	IRBB60
13	Navara	58	Aryan – 1102	103	ADT 37
14	Noothipathu	59	Shadabhar	104	Tetep
15	Kullakar	60	Keralakandasala		
16	Veethiruppu	61	Chembavu		
17	Swarnamasuri	62	Pusa Basumathi		
18	Aryan 6333	63	Kaivara Samba		
19	Chiruchitteni	64	kavuni		
20	Aryan 1203	65	Kuliyadichan		
21	Chitteni 520	66	Kallundaikar		
22	Navara 957	67	Orkaima		
23	Chembavu Chitteni	68	Meikuruvai		
24	Chenna	69	SriLanka		
25	Arupatham Kavuni	70	Adukan		
26	Karunkuruvai	71	Dhalaheera		
27	Keerai Samba	72	Anna 4		
28	Raja Guruvai	73	Chembavu 4331		
29	Sivan Samba	74	Kodivilaiyan		
30	Panangkaattu Vaazhai	75	Aryan - 5532		
31	Komban Samba	76	Mulampunchan		
32	Katti Samba	77	Channa Ponni		
33	Palkudavazai	78	Kalyani		
34	Oriza nettai	79	Geethanjali Basumathi		
35	Thanga Samba	80	Mozhikarumpu		
36	Kottara Samba	81	White Shannam		
37	Basumathi	82	Pant Sugandhi		
38	Vaikarai Samba	83	Pusa Sugandhi		
39	Rathali	84	Parithban		
40	Kothamalli Samba	85	Mahi Sugandhi		
41	Chithiraikar	86	Amman		
42	Sivappu Gowni	87	Jaisriram		
43	Arupatham Kuruvai	88	Virendra		
44	Milagu Samba	89	Mallikar		
45	Karuthakar	90	Seeraga Samba		

Table 2. ANOVA for all the eleven biometric traits of 104 rice genotypes studied

Source of variation	df	Mean Sum of Squares										
		DFE	PH	NT	NPT	PL	NFG	TGW	GL	GB	L/B ratio	SPY
Replication	2	8.9719	142.4399	3.2814	1.7298	1.7675	24.8232	0.9056	0.1580	0.0513	0.0079	1.7206
Treatment	103	185.8047**	2147.0622**	196.8329**	125.3440**	35.7411**	5898.1513**	96.7138**	3.8366**	0.8618**	1.1721**	1780.5375**
Error	206	19.9883	40.3271	1.7183	1.0941	1.2764	47.8993	1.5750	0.1623	0.0229	0.0214	8.7835

Table 3. Mean performance for all the eleven biometrical traits of 104 rice genotypes

Genotypes	Group	DFE	PH	NT	NPT	PL	NFG	1000GW	GL	GB	L/Bratio	SPY
Purpleputtu	Landrace	93.02	148.93	13.25	12.23	27.32*	268.50*	16.25	7.01	3.23*	2.66	52.39
Abiya	Landrace	90.00	145.76	13.50	11.50	25.41*	114.32	17.17	8.62*	3.12*	2.77	40.36
Chennakayamma	Landrace	98.51	107.26	13.31	10.21	21.53	98.06	19.23	9.13*	3.45*	0.36	40.65
Shabhagidhan	Landrace	85.53	124.23	21.04	18.00	22.09	96.35	18.22	8.50*	3.33*	2.83	32.14
Vattan	Landrace	84.05	117.90	21.52	20.50	19.02	143.11*	18.00	7.00	2.33	3.00*	53.01
Jaya	Landrace	90.00	119.96	24.50	21.53*	25.57*	170.24*	14.93	8.22*	2.62	3.15*	54.46*
Thamarai	Landrace	90.00	93.00*	18.34	16.31	21.60	95.03	23.24	7.01	2.66	2.63	35.68
Sivappumalli	Landrace	87.34	137.92	19.65	18.42	18.81	140.46*	29.95*	7.62	1.93	3.94*	20.75
Pisni	Landrace	85.42	134.53	28.00*	25.31*	23.24	73.33	28.00*	7.61	2.92	2.62	51.11
Kalanamak	Landrace	83.53	74.34*	22.50	19.50	26.24*	258.23*	28.50*	8.52*	3.23*	2.65	29.76
Kalakuruvai	Landrace	98.00	88.15*	28.54*	27.53*	21.15	122.73	29.08*	8.00*	2.91	2.76	97.99*
Rajalakshmi	Landrace	92.52	99.80*	25.53	22.51*	25.26*	140.75*	19.43	8.60*	2.62	3.28*	61.44*
Navara	Landrace	72.00*	94.13*	55.00*	52.54*	20.64	73.66	15.24	7.50	4.03*	1.86	58.01*
Noothipathu	Landrace	83.50	112.30	27.50*	24.52	24.83*	169.74*	22.14	6.80	2.93	2.32	91.88*
Kullakar	Landrace	84.55	122.26	22.24	20.51	26.41*	140.00*	19.43	7.31	2.80	2.50	55.68*
Veethiruppu	Landrace	85.51	149.73	23.99	17.20	21.13	156.79*	16.62	8.12*	2.61	3.11*	44.77
Swarnamasuri	Landrace	83.52	143.25	21.31	14.00	26.50*	220.39*	26.81*	5.94	3.22*	1.83	93.95*
Aryan 6333	Landrace	80.00	76.75*	18.42	16.34	18.22	113.31	27.63*	8.03*	3.51*	2.28	50.98
Chiruchitenni	Landrace	77.51*	145.33	16.30	13.03	15.41	161.02*	25.52*	7.21	2.81	2.49	53.38
Aryan 1203	Landrace	77.52*	142.25	21.03	21.54*	23.22	142.33*	28.24*	6.23	2.11	2.84	86.28*
Chitenni 520	Landrace	96.51	132.65	15.06	14.32	24.92*	163.53*	27.95*	6.61	2.54	2.62	65.23*
Navara 957	Landrace	84.00	136.06	18.15	18.07	21.43	146.82*	25.35*	5.92	2.63	2.24	68.66*
Chembavu chitenni	Landrace	91.54	106.86	25.61	14.20	26.54*	160.11*	25.41*	5.83	2.91	1.99	57.74*
Chenna	Landrace	92.03	96.53*	20.00	16.72	17.44	118.24	27.01*	9.00*	3.57*	2.52	53.21
Arupatham Kavuni	Landrace	92.50	141.00	22.15	20.34	20.01	143.17*	25.32*	6.52	2.37	2.75	72.50*

Karunkuruvai	Landrace	90.61	157.70	16.83	12.64	19.22	65.78	24.71*	5.94	2.94	2.01	20.55
Keerai Samba	Landrace	86.00	113.13	21.08	17.43	23.33	138.67	28.42*	5.62	2.11	2.65	28.77
Raja kuruvai	Landrace	79.50*	147.70	35.30*	24.30*	21.42	101.00	17.69	7.14	2.85	2.51	43.42
Sivan Samba	Landrace	85.59	130.43	18.20	17.51	20.14	150.36*	17.44	6.61	3.24*	2.04	45.81
Panangkaatu Vaazhai	Landrace	95.15	109.90	24.31	16.15	17.32	81.24	19.42	9.34*	4.06*	2.22	25.38
Komban Samba	Landrace	94.66	95.76*	26.00*	23.72*	22.14	56.51	36.01*	7.15	2.51	2.84	46.37
Katti Samba	Landrace	83.00	125.26	20.24	17.16	20.43	128.76	12.25	4.33	2.16	2.00	26.18
Palkuda Vazhai	Landrace	89.53	118.13	28.57*	21.36*	23.16	184.45*	22.37	5.26	1.42	3.52*	88.13*
Oriza nettai	Landrace	82.00	121.54	23.01	19.11	15.62	74.30	17.46	6.33	1.66	3.81*	24.15
Thanga Samba	Landrace	94.54	106.60	22.13	16.55	21.57	129.00	14.64	5.76	3.19*	1.81	11.48
Kottara Samba	Landrace	77.57*	142.93	26.48*	20.41	25.85*	83.94	16.55	8.45*	3.00	2.67	28.27
Basumathi	Landrace	90.53	180.65	20.06	18.00	19.99	129.54	18.32	6.60	1.80	3.67*	20.00
Vaikarai Samba	Landrace	87.00	83.36*	21.63	18.01	18.16	107.63	17.25	8.32*	3.52*	2.29	32.97
Rathali	Landrace	90.00	94.34*	30.00*	25.13*	19.94	110.92	16.15	8.21*	2.94	2.79	13.42
Kothamalli Samba	Landrace	86.00	146.77	20.36	14.02	19.92	81.24	25.21*	6.65	2.93	2.27	28.35
Chithiraikar	Landrace	82.53	162.86	27.16*	17.27	18.77	73.17	24.06*	6.94	3.34*	2.31	31.24
Sivappu kavuni	Landrace	89.55	106.36	22.76	18.41	21.22	188.42*	19.25	5.93	2.09	2.84	66.77*
Arupatham kuruvai	Landrace	77.56*	124.70	21.50	16.73	21.24	95.76	18.52	6.42	2.84	2.25	29.57
Milagu Samba	Landrace	96.06	109.33	28.91*	22.32*	20.38	115.24	15.63	5.16	2.48	2.08	23.12
Karuthakar	Landrace	92.50	158.13	17.02	13.15	17.45	116.37	22.83	6.21	2.71	2.30	34.65
Orisamani Samba	Landrace	75.68*	115.60	18.67	17.77	23.01	172.15*	20.00	5.54	3.23*	1.72	61.18*
Sengalpattu Sirumani	Landrace	84.55	132.10	31.44*	27.31*	19.24	124.37	16.44	7.01	3.55*	1.97	55.70*
Aathur Kichilisamba	Landrace	93.00	167.71	22.00	16.84	25.52*	206.82*	20.62	7.11	2.23	3.19*	71.63*
Karuppu kavuni	Landrace	98.00	156.66	25.93*	20.04	22.41	120.64	25.03*	6.32	2.42	3.15*	72.19*
Orisa kuttai Sivappu Arisi	Landrace	79.59*	163.10	29.16*	24.11*	26.11*	178.62*	21.89	8.97*	2.45	3.66*	94.26*

Ariyan	Landrace	87.64	157.00	19.24	18.11	25.06*	107.00	41.00*	8.53*	2.66	3.20*	79.95*
Oheruchitteni	Landrace	80.58	91.07*	29.32*	17.92	19.72	68.24	23.33	7.66	2.67	2.87*	27.37
Chennellu 6806	Landrace	88.00	118.86	25.00	21.45*	17.23	74.13	19.21	8.22*	2.22	3.70*	29.90
J-13 100 Days	Landrace	75.50*	101.93*	18.00	13.36	23.63	161.70*	19.46	8.55*	3.01	2.82	40.95
Mappillai Samba	Landrace	88.52	124.83	17.33	13.01	21.21	77.22	27.71*	6.64	3.61*	1.83	28.67
Kunju Kunju	Landrace	96.00	92.71*	27.00*	19.00	24.64*	150.93*	25.26*	7.43	3.23*	2.31	72.25*
Navara Black	Landrace	112.78	86.16*	25.33	22.63*	14.00	40.00	23.41	8.01*	3.24*	2.67	20.79
Ariyan 1102	Landrace	91.30	120.00	30.01*	23.44*	24.40*	119.18	13.66	8.53*	3.13*	2.83	38.15
Shadabhar	Landrace	74.55*	149.55	18.98	16.97	23.51	150.65*	24.92*	7.53	3.10*	2.50	63.66*
Kerala Kandhasala	Landrace	76.64*	93.16*	23.51	21.65*	21.62	77.25	23.00	8.33*	2.51	3.32*	37.35
Chembavu	Landrace	86.58	110.72	11.37	11.74	17.72	90.11	16.63	7.33	2.54	2.89*	16.91
Pusa Basumathi	Landrace	95.54	91.00*	23.25	20.35	16.13	47.39	18.65	9.03*	3.11*	3.01*	17.96
Kaivara samba	Landrace	97.56	118.00	14.87	10.93	29.22*	115.30	20.00	9.66*	2.33	4.15*	25.07
kavuni	Landrace	84.00	102.86*	14.11	7.86	26.31*	150.50*	14.53	8.82*	3.72*	2.38	17.15
Kuliyadichan	Landrace	94.50	101.13*	21.57	16.43	21.82	119.58	13.28	8.81*	3.63*	2.44	25.93
Kallundaikar	Landrace	80.50	94.14*	20.00	18.64	27.90*	78.00	30.67*	9.32*	4.07*	2.21	43.99
Orkaima	Landrace	76.51*	141.65	29.17*	20.00	22.00	111.61	13.93	8.12*	3.05	2.66	31.04
Meikuruvai	Landrace	96.00	102.95*	19.65	14.12	20.73	69.04	21.11	8.23*	3.06*	2.68	20.46
SriLanka	Landrace	89.34	97.78*	14.98	12.28	21.44	189.15*	17.13	6.21	2.70	2.22	39.49
Adukan	Landrace	96.64	92.61*	25.58	19.14	18.91	102.38	16.29	8.66*	1.96	4.42*	31.27
Dhaluheera	Landrace	92.55	87.80*	19.24	11.16	21.73	77.00	31.55*	8.00*	3.54*	2.26	26.73
Anna 4	Landrace	81.54	104.91*	29.99*	26.51*	28.03*	178.69*	19.42	7.66	2.66	2.88*	89.99*
Chembavu 4331	Landrace	86.00	149.07	19.00	14.34	22.25	159.93*	29.58*	4.70	3.67*	1.28	66.05*
Kodivilaiyan	Landrace	86.64	98.16*	33.17*	26.76*	25.51*	139.75*	24.93*	8.30*	2.63	3.16*	92.99*
Aryan - 5532	Landrace	77.52*	148.50	26.00*	24.64*	25.67*	154.33*	19.95	5.93	3.24*	1.82	75.55*
Mulampunchan	Landrace	77.58*	135.24	15.98	15.02	24.00*	170.56*	23.57	6.62	2.53	2.61	60.20*
China Ponna	Landrace	97.59	159.45	27.49*	17.00	22.62	92.64	23.00	8.66*	1.83	4.73*	35.97
Kalyani	Landrace	82.00	167.37	17.52	16.78	18.94	65.34	26.47*	7.51	3.01	2.49	28.87
Geethanjali	Landrace	83.50	77.40*	15.11	11.83	21.63	86.70	35.82*	8.74*	3.65*	2.38	36.63

Basumathi												
Mozhi Karumbu	Landrace	95.01	103.51*	15.55	13.47	23.17	105.15	19.48	8.34*	2.33	3.43*	26.67
White Shannam	Landrace	90.25	92.79*	20.23	13.10	20.65	76.11	13.46	8.00*	4.00*	2.00	13.34
Pant Sugandhi	Landrace	90.50	106.56	22.11	20.61	18.21	96.81	19.09	7.42	2.24	3.31*	38.09
Pusa Sugandhi	Landrace	98.72	83.19*	15.16	14.09	20.13	106.31	30.56*	8.00*	3.51*	2.28	44.95
Parithban	Landrace	87.00	80.06*	25.68	25.00*	23.86*	117.85	18.02	7.22	3.01	2.40	53.03
Mahi Sugandhi	Landrace	87.52	97.37*	28.25*	25.92*	24.00*	126.87	19.55	6.59	2.77	2.38	64.29*
Amman	Landrace	85.56	114.68	24.10	18.31	27.91*	141.34*	21.16	8.80*	3.54*	2.49	54.66*
Jaisriram	Landrace	89.57	94.80*	20.09	14.24	23.47	155.23*	15.29	7.00	3.16*	2.22	33.81
Virendra	Landrace	84.54	113.43	71.00*	49.39*	23.82*	146.13*	13.57	6.67	2.66	2.51	97.85*
Mallikar	Landrace	94.00	117.43	19.26	16.34	13.00	141.22*	20.66	6.43	3.02	1.99	48.47
Seeraga Samba	Landrace	76.00*	111.75	24.03	17.03	27.55*	155.10*	35.00*	7.66	2.67	2.87*	92.23*
Harathi	Landrace	95.53	134.21	40.34*	26.00*	18.91	241.31*	9.71	6.21	2.53	2.37	56.47*
Karuthanavara	Landrace	105.21	105.31	39.14*	31.10*	10.91	140.66*	21.63	5.41	2.95	1.83	94.62*
Chiruchitenni-882	Landrace	82.34	125.62	35.54*	25.67*	24.44*	152.21*	25.44*	7.00	2.02	3.51*	99.26*
Chomala-2206	Landrace	77.50*	116.50	37.23*	27.24*	18.56	74.31	16.97	8.20*	2.51	3.19*	32.11
Aryan-1204	Landrace	111.00	83.76*	33.00*	24.22*	20.60	90.00	22.57	8.12*	2.67	3.02*	48.35
NL 24	Variety	83.58	106.76	24.98	23.31*	24.57*	68.60	18.37	7.00	3.00	2.33	29.03
ASD 16	Variety	73.98*	66.53*	17.01	16.00	23.12	160.11*	19.53	6.85	2.23	3.07	50.03
RpBioPatho 1	Variety	74.21*	69.84*	20.42	18.65	19.73	158.35*	17.27	8.00*	3.44*	2.66	51.00
TPS 5	Variety	81.74	73.30*	31.00*	29.25*	22.94	182.24*	22.03	6.73	2.68	2.51	116.42*
RpBioPatho 2	Variety	83.25	72.65*	21.38	20.13	21.11	174.52*	18.00	7.13	2.52	2.80	62.82*
TRY 3	Variety	93.56	74.51*	21.81	18.54	26.94*	162.53*	21.54	6.22	2.50	2.48	57.00*
IRBB60	Variety	84.53	60.68*	20.24	16.38	21.47	143.55*	21.27	6.71	2.51	2.67	40.59
ADT 37	Variety	75.00*	89.91*	25.36	22.00*	25.20*	175.31*	26.82*	8.30*	3.32*	2.52	103.43*
Tetep	Variety	75.24*	102.33*	24.73	18.17	26.32*	133.18	16.73	6.08	2.28	2.67	36.41
Grand mean		87.13	115.13	23.67	19.26	21.96	127.77	21.57	7.29	2.82	2.64	49.15
S.E.		2.58	3.67	0.76	0.60	0.65	3.99	0.72	0.23	0.09	0.08	1.71
C. D. (5%)		7.15	10.16	2.10	1.67	1.81	11.08	2.01	0.64	0.24	0.23	4.74

C. V (%)		5.13	5.52	5.54	5.43	5.14	5.42	5.82	5.53	5.36	5.55	6.03
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